

Thermochromic Behaviour of Buffered Indicator Solutions. Part-III. Thermodynamic Values for the Transfer of Neutral Red from Water to Aqueous Methanol

F. H. JUMEAN* and M. I. QADERI

Department of Chemistry, University of Jordan, Amman, Jordan

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The thermochromic method was applied to the determination of thermodynamic values for the transfer of the indicator neutral red from water to aqueous solutions containing 10, 20 and 30% methanol by weight. Apparent values for the enthalpy, free energy, entropy and heat capacity of transfer were obtained and the medium effect term, $\log (\gamma_{In}^{\circ} / \gamma_{HI_n}^{\circ})$, was estimated.

THERMOCHROMACY or the variation of optical density with temperature, has been shown to provide a reliable basis for obtaining ionisation parameters for buffers and indicators¹. That thermodynamic study, however, was confined to solutions containing buffer (B) and indicator (I) for which the difference between the apparent heat capacities of ionisation, $\Delta C'_{p(B)} - \Delta C'_{p(I)}$, was insignificant. In a subsequent investigation², data were collected on systems for which the heat capacity terms differed substantially and the following equation was derived,

$$\log R = a/T - b + cT \quad (1)$$

where, R is the ratio of the base to the acid forms of the indicator, T the temperature (K), and a , b and c are constants. It was further shown that the differences between the apparent enthalpies and heat capacities for buffer and indicator are given by,

$$\Delta(\Delta H') = \Delta H'_B - \Delta H'_I = 2.303 R (a - cT^2) \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta(\Delta C'_p) = \Delta C'_{p(B)} - \Delta C'_{p(I)} = -4.606 R cT \quad (3)$$

These equations were derived on the condition that the buffer activity ratio, a_{HB}/a_{B^-} , and the indicator activity coefficient ratio, $\gamma_{In}/\gamma_{HI_n}$, are both insensitive to temperature variations. The validity of these two provisions was shown to be adequate. In this work, the treatment of the medium effect requires the inclusion of free energy and entropy terms. These are given by,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta(\Delta G') &= \Delta G'_B - \Delta G'_I = 2.303 \log R \\ &= 2.303 R (a - bT + cT^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta(\Delta S') = \Delta S'_B - \Delta S'_I = 2.303 R (b - 2cT) \quad (5)$$

Equation (4) is obtained from equation (2) with the aid of the Gibbs-Helmholtz relation and equation (5) follows immediately from equation (4).

The present study aims at testing the applicability of the thermochromic method towards the attain-

ment of thermodynamic values for the transfer of ionic species from water to a nonaqueous medium. These values are highly valuable to the understanding of the behaviour of ions in such a medium. In order to obtain the transfer values, it is essential to evaluate firstly the differences between the thermodynamic values for the ionisation of buffer and indicator (equations 2-5) for each medium. Runs were made on solutions containing the indicator neutral red, the buffer sodium dihydrogen phosphate, in water and in aqueous solutions containing 10, 20 and 30% methanol by weight. The ionisation parameters for the indicator were then calculated by making use of the corresponding reported^{3,4} values for the buffer. The value of a given thermodynamic parameter in a nonaqueous medium is then obtained directly by subtraction of the ionisation value in water from the ionisation value in the medium. This indicator neutral red was selected because preliminary measurements revealed that in the presence of sodium dihydrogen phosphate as buffer, its solutions in water and in aqueous methanol exhibited a high degree of thermochromicity, sharp isosbestic points and a completely reversible temperature effect. In addition, the reported pK for this indicator (7.4 at 25°)⁵ in water was sufficiently close to that of the buffer (7.200 at 25°)⁶ to ensure good buffering capacity as well as a high sensitivity of measurement.

The free energy of an ionic species i in a nonaqueous solvent may be referred to a standard state in water or to one in the solvent. The difference between the values of these standard states is the free energy of transfer of i from water to the solvent. This is related to the medium effect, γ_m , as

$$\Delta G_i^{\circ} = G_i^{\circ} - G_w^{\circ} = 2.303 \log \gamma_m \quad (6)$$

The medium effect is thus seen to be a conversion factor between the two scales and is equivalent to

the activity ratio, ${}_w a_1/a_2$. For neutral red, whose charge type is A^+B^0 , the ionisations in water and in aqueous methanol are

According to equation (6), the transfer of one mole each of HIn^+ , In and H^+ from water to the mixed solvent has the following free energy,

$$\Delta G_t^0 = \Delta G_s^0 - \Delta G_w^0 = 2.303 RT \log ({}_m \gamma_{H^+} \cdot {}_m \gamma_{In} / {}_m \gamma_{HIn}) \quad (8)$$

Single ion medium effects, just like single ions activity coefficients, are of course incapable of being determined by a rigorous thermodynamic method. There are, however, several 'extrathermodynamic' methods, each relying on its own set of assumptions, for such calculations⁷⁻⁹. Thus by employing an estimated value for ${}_m \gamma_{H^+}$ for the transfer from water to aqueous methanol, it becomes possible to estimate the medium effect ratio, ${}_m \gamma_{In} / {}_m \gamma_{HIn}$, for the indicator.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade and used without further purification. pH and spectral measurements were performed in the manner described earlier². The optical density values at 528 nm were selected for calculating R terms, since at this wavelength the optical densities of the acid and base forms had the highest ratio (D_{acid}/D_{base} varied from 5.61 in water to 6.40 in 30% methanol). The ionic strength of all solutions was maintained at 0.050 M by the addition of sodium chloride.

Results and Discussion

For all the solutions investigated, the maxima for the acid and base forms of the indicator were located at 528 and 454 nm, respectively, with an isosbestic point at 474 nm. The R values were calculated using the equation $R = (D - D_b)/(D_a - D)$, where D is the optical density of the solution, and D_a and D_b are the optical densities of the acid and base forms of the indicator, respectively. The molar extinction coefficients for neutral red at 528 nm varied at 25° from $2.25 \times 10^5 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ m}^2$ in water to $2.64 \times 10^5 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ m}^2$ in 30% methanol, with a concomitant sharpening of the absorption bands as the percentage of methanol is raised. For all the solutions studied, the buffer concentration was maintained at 0.010 M whereas that of the indicator was varied in the vicinity of 10^{-6} M . The addition of methanol causes an initial small drop in the pK value of the indicator. This drop necessitated a lowering of the pH for the more highly methanolic solutions in order to maintain an adequate ratio of the acid to base forms of the absorbing species. All measurements were confined to the pH range 6.9–7.4. The pH values in the mixed solvent were adjusted to the aqueous scale by using

the equation¹⁰, $pH_s = pH_w - \delta$, where δ is a small positive constant. It should be noted, however, that the precise values for the concentration of buffer and indicator do not have a direct influence on the R value. These concentrations were selected in order to ensure a good buffering capacity and high sensitivity of optical density to temperature. At any given temperature, the R value is a function of pH, but the shape of the $\log R$ vs $1/T$ plot is not. Thus the pH values were adjusted for the purpose of enhancing the sensitivity of measurement without exerting a direct influence on the constants of equation (1). As for the optical density at 528 nm, it experienced a substantial drop upon raising the temperature. For example, in 20% methanol, the optical density for a solution containing $6.67 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$ indicator dropped from 1.107 at 6.7° to only 0.629 at 51.5°.

Fig. 1 shows the dependence of $\log R$ on $1/T$ for solutions in water and in the mixed solvent. The

Fig. 1. Dependence of $\log R$ on $1/T$ for buffer-indicator solutions in 0, 10, 20 and 30% aqueous methanol by weight. For clarity, the 20 and 30 percent curves are moved up the vertical axis a distance of 0.2 and 0.4 units, respectively, and the water curve is moved down 0.2 units.

TABLE 1—CONSTANTS FOR EQUATION (1) AND THE APPARENT THERMODYNAMIC DIFFERENCE VALUES AT 298.15 K AS A FUNCTION OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION

	Methanol % (by weight)			
	0	10	20	30
a	3736	2988	1939	-436.3
b	27.54	23.33	17.42	2.22
c	0.050	0.045	0.037	0.013
T_{\max} (K)	273.3	257.7	228.9	—
$\Delta(\Delta H')(\pm 0.12, \text{kJ mol}^{-1})$	-13.57	-19.38	-25.85	-30.48
$\Delta(\Delta G')(\pm 0.03, \text{kJ mol}^{-1})$	-0.582	0.620	0.656	1.10
$\Delta(\Delta S')(\pm 4, \text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1})$	-43.6	-67.1	-88.9	-106
$\Delta(\Delta C'_p)(\pm 12, \text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1})$	-571	-514	-422	-148

TABLE 2—APPARENT THERMODYNAMIC VALUES FOR THE IONISATION OF BUFFER (B) AND INDICATOR (I) AT 298.15 K AS A FUNCTION OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION

	Methanol % (by weight)			
	0	10	20	30
$\Delta H'_B$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	4.129	4.698	4.874	3.924 ^a
$\Delta G'_B$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	41.10	42.04	43.38	44.24 ^a
$\Delta S'_B$ (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-123	-125	-129	-138 ^a
$\Delta C'_{pB}$ (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-226	-268	-247	-251 ^a
$\Delta H'_I$ ($\pm 0.12, \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$)	17.70	24.08	30.72	34.40
$\Delta G'_I$ ($\pm 0.03, \text{kJ mol}^{-1}$)	41.68	41.42	42.73	43.14
$\Delta S'_I$ ($\pm 3, \text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	-79.4	-57.9	-40.1	-32.1
$\Delta C'_{pI}$ ($\pm 12, \text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	345	246	175	-103

*Ref. 3. ^aInterpolations from Ref. 10.

curves are best-fits to equation (1) and were obtained with the aid of a linear regression computer program. For better clarity and contrast, these curves have been spaced apart, in the manner indicated, by moving them up or down with respect to the log R axis. This procedure does not, of course, affect the values of the constants of equation (1) or the calculated thermodynamic quantities, since these depend on the overall shape of the curves, which is not affected. Table 1 lists the values of the constants of equation (1) and the apparent thermodynamic property differences of equations (2-5). Values for $(1/T)_{\min}$ or T_{\max} are also tabulated. This is the temperature corresponding to the minimum of the log R vs $1/T$ curve and is readily shown to have the value of $(a/c)^{1/2}$ by differentiation of equation (1). It is noted that the value of T_{\max} decreases from 273.3 K in water to 228.9 K in 20% methanol. This decrease parallels the drop in the values of $\Delta(\Delta C'_p)$, which accounts for the curves becoming less convex to the $1/T$ axis as methanol is added. When the 30% methanol composition is finally reached, the $\Delta(\Delta C'_p)$ value is low ($148 \pm 12 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$), and thus the convexity is so small that no minimum exists (negative T). Table 1 also reveals a considerable and progressive change in the value of $\Delta(\Delta H')$, which ranges from -13.57 ± 0.12 in water to $-30.48 \pm 0.12 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ in 30% methanol. The trend in the apparent enthalpy difference is evident in Fig. 1, which exhibits progressively higher slopes with increasing methanol content. The results summarised in Fig. 1 and Table 1 were obtained from data collected in five separate runs.

Table 2 lists the apparent thermodynamic ionisation parameters pertinent to the buffer and indicator separately. For the buffer, the values given for the 0, 10 and 20% methanol solutions were obtained by Ender and coworkers³ whereas those for the 30% solution are interpolations from data listed by Bates and Robinson¹⁰. It is noteworthy that the apparent enthalpy of ionisation of the indicator, $\Delta H'_I$, is highly sensitive to solvent composition, rising from a value of 17.70 ± 0.12 in water to $34.40 \pm 0.12 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ in 30% methanol. By contrast, the apparent free energy term, $\Delta G'_I$, is not markedly dependent on the medium. For example, its values in water and in 30% methanol are 41.68 ± 0.03 and $43.14 \pm 0.03 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. The variation in the $\Delta H'_I$ values may thus be attributed to a predominantly entropic origin. The absence of significant differences in the $\Delta G'_I$ values is consistent with the indicator belonging to the charge type A^+B^0 with ionisations described by equation (7). Such ionisations are not accompanied by either the creation or destruction of charge. Hence, the change in the electrostatic component of the free energy is expected to be very small and the observed free energy change may be wholly ascribed to terms of nonelectrostatic origin, related chiefly to the nature of the solvent. The entropy change, $\Delta S'_I$, varies from a value of -79.4 ± 3 in water to $-32.1 \pm 3 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in 30% methanol. Thus the ionisation of the indicator is accompanied by a significant increase in order. This ordering may be attributed to the creation of a proton, which

due to its small size and considerable electric field, surrounds itself with highly ordered water molecules in an 'ice-like' cage. The observation that $\Delta S_t'$ become less negative with methanol addition is consistent with the hypothesis⁷ that methanol addition weakens the 'ice-like' structure of water.

Table 3 lists the apparent thermodynamic values for the transfer from water to the mixed solvent. The apparent enthalpies of transfer, $\Delta H_t'$, are positive and increase from a value of 6.38 ± 0.17 for the transfer to 10% methanol to 16.70 ± 0.17 kJ mol⁻¹ for the 30% solvent. The free energy of transfer, $\Delta G_t'$, also rises with methanol addition. Its values, however, are quite small, ranging from only -0.26 ± 0.04 in water to 1.46 ± 0.04 kJ mol⁻¹ in 30% methanol. Table 3 also gives values for the apparent entropy of transfer, $\Delta S_t'$. The relatively large increase in this parameter from a value of 21.5 ± 4 for the transfer to 10% methanol to 47.3 ± 4 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ for the transfer to the 30% solvent, is again consistent with the idea of water-cage destruction by methanol.

Table 3 also lists the free energies of transfer of the hydrogen ion from water to the various solvents, as estimated by Feakins⁷. Substitution of these values in equations (6) and (8) yield values for the term $\log (m\gamma_{In}/m\gamma_{HIn^+})$, corresponding to the medium effect ratio of the indicator species. Furthermore, since each $\Delta G_t'$ term may be written as the sum of an electrostatic and a nonelectrostatic component, it follows from equation (6) that each medium effect term is the product of two such components. Thus, if the reasonable assumption is then made that the nonelectrostatic values for the medium

TABLE 3—APPARENT THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE TRANSFER OF NEUTRAL RED, AT 298.15 K, FROM WATER TO AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS CONTAINING DIFFERENT PERCENTAGE OF METHANOL

	Methanol % (by weight)		
	10	20	30
$\Delta H_t'$ (± 0.17 , kJ mol ⁻¹)	6.38	13.02	16.70
$\Delta G_t'$ (± 0.04 , kJ mol ⁻¹)	-0.26	1.05	1.46
$\Delta S_t'$ (± 4 , J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	21.5	39.3	47.3
$\Delta G_{p,t}$ (± 17 , J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-99	-170	-248
ΔG_t (H ⁺) ^a	-2.09	-3.81	-6.80 ^a
$\log (m\gamma_{In}/m\gamma_{HIn^+})$	-0.921	0.853	1.45

^aRef. 7. ^aInterpolated value.

effect of the species In and HIn⁺ are equivalent, it becomes possible to identify the term $\log (m\gamma_{In}/m\gamma_{HIn^+})$ with one containing a single medium effect, $-\log (m\gamma_{HIn^+})_{el}$.

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